

Secure and Privacy-Preserving Car-Sharing Systems

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ABSTRACT

With increasing smart transportation systems and services, potential security and privacy threats are growing. In this work, we analyze privacy and security threats in car-sharing systems, and discuss the problems with the transparency of services, users' personal data collection, and how the legislation manages these issues. Based on analyzed requirements, we design a compact privacy-preserving solution for car-sharing systems. Our proposal combines digital signature schemes and group signature schemes, in order to protect user privacy against curious providers, increase security and non-repudiation, and be efficient even for systems with restricted devices. The evaluation of the proposed solution demonstrates its security and a practical usability for constrained devices deployed in vehicles and users' smartphones.

CCS CONCEPTS

• Security and privacy → Authentication; Privacy-preserving protocols; Access control; Pseudonymity, anonymity and untraceability.

KEYWORDS

Access Control, Anonymous Digital Signature, Applied Cryptography, Authentication, Benchmarks, Group Signature, Privacy, Security

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1 INTRODUCTION

Security and privacy properties should be natively incorporated into modern digital services. Only public Car-Sharing Systems (CSS) that keep users' privacy and also the security of assets (vehicles)

can be successful in practice. The crucial phases are acquiring, getting access to vehicles, and their correct return. Privacy-preserving methods can help to address many privacy requirements such as unlinkability and pseudonymous accesses. Cryptography and security tools can address security requirements such as authenticity, integrity, and non-repudiation.

Currently, smartphone applications are the most common method for users to access these car-sharing services. Smartphones serve as the primary interface between digital services and users, posing a significant challenge to balancing user privacy with the car-sharing system's functionality. Legal regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA), and Digital Service Act (DSA), provide governance across different countries of operation and encourage to protect the privacy of users. Enhancing privacy through integrating proper methods and software design of applications that interact with the service is essential. Employing suitable cryptography, security measures, and system approaches known as Privacy-Enhancing Technologies (PETs) can significantly increase user data privacy. Nevertheless, the system needs also to keep data integrity, non-repudiation, and authenticity in order to protect the assets. All these requirements can be addressed by a proper composition of advanced security and cryptography methods. For instance, Group Signatures (GS) as popular PETs can be implemented in a wide range of scenarios where users require anonymity while also allowing the system the required traceability of misbehaving users. In group signatures, the user can sign anonymously on behalf of a group. The verifier or other users can validate the group signature with just one public key (a group public key). In the typical use case of car-sharing services, authorized users can gain access to a selected shared vehicle by using group signatures. The users generate group signatures with their secret keys by using the car-sharing application on their smartphones. In the vehicles, simple single-board devices can be used for access verification to these users and unlock the cars to valid users.

In this work, we focus closely on current privacy-preserving car-sharing systems by studying the state-of-the-art, and we analyze concrete threats in these systems. Based on this analysis, we present a novel solution that deploys group signatures but is also practical for small and middle public car-sharing systems where vehicles are equipped with small and partly-constrained devices used for checking user access requests.

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1.1 Contributions and Paper Organization

This work focuses on the privacy-preserving design of a car-sharing system and addresses two main research questions.

- Question Q1: What are current security and privacy threats in car-sharing services and which privacy-preserving techniques can be used and suitable?
- Question Q2: How to design a cryptographically secure car-sharing system that protects users' privacy and is practical for deployment on constrained devices and handheld devices used by users and vehicles?

Section 2 identifies the current state-of-the-art in the car-sharing systems, as this is a new and rapidly evolving area of research. Section 3 briefly discusses how the legal regulation is implemented in the services towards their users. Further, threat analysis and offered suitable PETs are also described. This section reflects Q1. Section 4 presents the main proposal with a high-level description of the architecture and system phases. Section 5 evaluates and discusses the proposal's security and performance. These sections reflect Q2. Section 6 concludes the results and points to future work.

2 RELATED WORK

Privacy-preserving technologies and security solutions for car-sharing systems are still considered a new field of research and have been studied in numerous works in recent years.

Arm *et al.* [1] designed a system that consists of an embedded device to access the car, a back-end server and a mobile app, and described the flow of the car-sharing process. The paper also addressed issues concerning security, safety and privacy. Auer *et al.* [2] explored a conceptual design on how to use blockchain and IoT technologies to increase the shared mobility process. Cao *et al.* [5] proposed an identity authentication key-exchange protocol that uses biometrics and passwords as authentication methods. Combining both features strengthens data protection and security performance. Dzurenda *et al.* [7] presented a system where users of the car-sharing service can access the car without the need to share physical keys between owners of the car and the user with emphasis on security, privacy and also low computational demands. In [13], Kim *et al.* proposed a decentralized car-sharing system which could reduce the single-point entry attacks that are faced by centralized car-sharing systems. The authors introduce a secure authentication scheme for the car-sharing system to withstand different threats and vulnerabilities that the system may face thereby granting privacy-preserving access to the cars. Ma *et al.* [15] discussed the verification of the users to curb the potential privacy security issues that arise when a user decides to rent a car. The method deals firstly with the verification of the driver in real-time and suggests an anomaly operation detection module that monitors the behaviour of the driver and the car throughout the driving cycle. In [17], Pollicino *et al.* proposed an architecture that enables people to share their cars with prospective users through intermediate brokers. Cheng *et al.* [6] investigated the influences of perceived risks and how the trade-off between perceived risks and benefits affects people's information privacy choices in the context of IT-enabled ride-sharing. Safdar *et al.* [18] explained the perception of people's acceptance of the car-sharing systems iterating concerns on how users perceive the data collected during this service. The study

describes how the factors of security and privacy could influence users of shared mobility.

In increasing the trust in car-sharing, Moreno *et al.* [16] stated that for users to gain trust in how information is shared within a system, the identity management system relied heavily on centralized methods of probing and mitigating risks of identity spoofing and loss of identity information. Bossauer *et al.* [4] looked towards creating trust for users in Peer-to-Peer (P2P) car-sharing and explore the need to protect users' information to increase trust in the system. Liu *et al.* [14] proposed a scheme to protect user's details during authentication. The protection of the user's personal information does not affect the websites or apps as they are not allowed to store any copy of the user's information. Symeonidis *et al.* [20] described a SePCAR protocol where users can use shared cars without disclosing their private data to the companies. The protocol is based on four steps: Session keys generation and data distribution, access token generation, access token distribution and verification, and car access. Their decentralized SePCAR solution provides security and privacy-enhancing features including unlinkability and anonymity by encrypted booking details. SePCAR's car access provision takes around 1.55 s. Valastin *et al.* [21] described how to use non-fungible tokens to unlock a car and the car owner in this scenario would be given complete full control of how their personal information is accessed. Wei *et al.* [22] proposed a secure key-sharing system known as the hierarchical identity-based signature key sharing, which consists of key generation, key transmission, and key management in the context of protecting the car and how users can have access to the cars based on their identity and the keys generated distributed to the car users through their smartphones. Zhou *et al.* [23] introduced a decentralized control scheme based on a smart contract to reduce several threats posed by the car-sharing system due to a centralized architecture.

The most relevant work was done by Groza *et al.* [9] who preserved the anonymity of users by group signatures in access to vehicles. They implemented the group signature scheme BBS04 [3] and measured this on mobile platforms. Their implementation of BBS04 takes 24 ms for signing and 33 ms for verification on Samsung S7. Other tested devices had slower times (hundreds ms). Groza *et al.*'s solution adds an identity-based scheme to avoid certificates and also engages manufacturers and sellers in the phases that could be problematic in a heterogeneous automotive world. In our solution, we avoid this complex integration and orient toward add-on solutions without manufacturers and sellers. We are focusing on a privacy-preserving, secure, and efficient approach that will be practical for small-middle car-sharing systems. The design should contain a simple system model and well-established technologies and methods that can be deployed.

3 ANALYSIS OF SECURITY AND PRIVACY IN SHARED VEHICLE SYSTEMS

The goal of this section is to give brief insights into current legislative aspects, typical threats and approaches that protect user privacy in car-sharing.

3.1 On Legislative and Privacy Aspects of Car-Sharing Systems

Car-sharing system users can be sometimes faced with two options while using services: **accept the terms and conditions** or **give up the comfort of shared mobility**. These terms are typically long, filled with legal language, and hardly read by users. Some providers can leverage this situation to their advantage, putting pressure on users to accept it without considering the impact on their data security and privacy.

The **privacy terms** offer the user a reasonably detailed theoretical explanation of the handling of personal data during the use of the services. However, only to the necessary legal depth that is required by the company in terms of compilation with the GDPR, CCPA or DSA regulation. Car-sharing systems have moved on, due to the pandemic, significantly since the implementation of the GDPR (2018) and its wider legislative scope is not adequate nowadays, and EU and US regimes for regulating data protection can be very different. For example, location history, driving behavior, or smartphone metadata are a few specific collected data that are hardly addressed by the legislation. It is leaving a "grey zone" for the company to determine how to handle these users' data and consents. Furthermore, services have to find a **delicate balance** between user security and privacy while maintaining a **profitable business model**. Besides, users and providers also collaborate with multiple parties such as:

- State agencies – license validation, car registration, and tax compliance;
- Insurance companies – covering any accident or car theft;
- Bank institutes – car leasing, service expansion;
- Law enforcement – in cases of misuse or improper vehicle use;
- Business – market analysis, expanding, stakeholders.

These collaborations may involve massive data sharing, but the challenge is to minimize the impact on user privacy. Obtaining such a right balance can be a long-term job, involving all of the aforementioned parties and their transition to PETs which significantly improve user data security and privacy across multiple fields.

Car-sharing system environment is highly competitive, demanding to operate, and **prioritizes customer satisfaction**. The main goal of the CSS is to maximize car utilization to reduce traffic congestion and increase environmental impact, while simultaneously providing a simple and affordable service. More satisfied customers using the service means a bigger market advantage. From a technical perspective, many CSS available on the market are closed source, meaning that the user is only informed of privacy conditions, containing generic phrases like "*collecting minimal user data necessary*", "*prioritize users privacy*" or "*using best practices in the field*". Typically backed by International Organization for Standardization (ISO) certification, but sometimes with **no mechanism for the user to independently confirm the accuracy of the claims**.

On the other hand, the continuous implementation of stricter data privacy laws (*GDPR, CCPA, DSA*) has increased the **transparency** of how user data are processed, under what type of consent the data are collected and if they are subject to automated profiling at least on a theoretical level. Storage period reasons that limit the complete erasure of user data after discontinuing the use

of the service are also explained in more detail, including *service operation, tax and billing reasons, contractual or legal obligations, etc.* However, giving consent upon the sign-up process and then using the service remains easier than revoking it.

3.2 Threats Analysis and Models for Shared Vehicle Systems

In car-sharing scenarios, data and information are exchanged among various involved parties. These include *identity details* and *login credentials, booking details, reservation details* and *car access tokens*. Information (e.g., *real-time information*) is shared among actors who deal with the user behavior while he/she is using the sharing service. In a payment process, the parties share *payment details*. All these types of data and information should be protected in the car-sharing scenarios.

There are numerous security risks to negate the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the information. For instance, the **man-in-the-middle attack** describes how the threat agent inserts itself into a communication between a user and an application, either to eavesdrop or to impersonate one of the parties. The **impersonation attack** explains how the threat agent pretends to be the user and impersonates the legitimate user of the application, thus, potentially, leading to the stealing of identity details and login credentials.

Data tampering attack can be performed to compromise the data between the identity provider while storing the details of the user. The attack can disrupt the integrity of the messages sent between the user and service provider thus compromising the car access token. In this way, the threat agent can get access to the car. Tampering attacks impact the integrity and confidentiality of users' identity details and car booking details.

Because of a single point of entry, servers and centralized servers depending on a central node to manage data and to operate the system can be exploited by the threat agent using **SQL injection (server leakage attack)**. This can potentially lead to the negation of integrity and confidentiality of data managed in these servers. **Denial of Service (DOS)** attack, the threat agent can overwhelm the service provider with numerous car access requests and booking requests thereby overwhelming the system's capacity and preventing genuine access requests from being processed.

During the **unauthorized access** attack, a threat agent could intercept and hijack sessions, when the service provider grants access to the user to access the car. The attack leads to the over-taking of the control of users' accounts to perform the car access action on their behalf without their knowledge. This attack could result in a compromise of the communication sessions between the service provider and the user in accessing the car. **Phishing** is one of the most frequent security attacks nowadays. The threat agent could get access to the information of a user by masquerading as a legitimate entity. Besides different impacts, this attack could lead to the communication protocol being unreliable and not trustworthy, theft of identity details and/or login credentials.

3.3 Suitable Privacy-Enhancing Technologies

In the context of car-sharing systems, these cryptographic techniques could enhance security and privacy by addressing specific

properties. This list is not exhaustive but contains basic categories of PETs:

- **Data Anonymization Techniques** - could consist of data masking, pseudonymization, or generalization, and are easy to use PETs for privacy protection of huge volumes of data in CSS. These techniques usually include masking vehicle license plates and user IDs in trip records, generalizing trip start/end locations to neighborhoods, or editing drive names in CSS.
- **Secure Multi-party Computation (SMPC)** - allows multiple parties to perform computations on their inputs without revealing their personal inputs to each other. It solves problems with a lack of confidence and increases transparency, anonymity, and data integrity/authenticity. However, it also comes with some disadvantages in terms of high computational complexity, scalability, and requirements for correct implementation. SMPC can be used in the CSS to calculate the price per ride, average trip distance, and more, without revealing individual user data.
- **Zero-Knowledge Proofs (ZKP)** - are generic methods that provide completeness, correctness, soundness, and zero knowledge. In CSS, ZKP could prove a user's valid driver's license without disclosing personal details or could verify compliance with traffic rules – speeding or parking restrictions. ZKP are usually used in more advanced and complete cryptographic schemes.
- **Group Signatures (GS)** - GS schemes offer security and privacy properties such as anonymity/pseudonymity, data authenticity and integrity, correctness, unforgeability, traceability, unlinkability, revocation, and more. When users want anonymously access to the vehicle they can simply prove their access token with a certain time validity by using a group signature. The provider or the verifier device in the vehicle can simply verify this signed token that was produced anonymously by the valid group member. The disadvantage of GS is their higher computational expensiveness which can cause delays and data overheads.

4 PROPOSED PRIVACY-PRESERVING CAR-SHARING SOLUTION

In this section, we present our proposed solution of secure privacy-preserving access to shared vehicles that can be deployed in public car-sharing systems.

4.1 High-level Description and Architecture

We assume open (sub)urban city car-sharing systems with strong security and privacy properties. All system phases are designed in order to minimize privacy leaks and keep strong security assumptions protecting users and providers' assets. The proposed framework architecture is depicted in Figure 1. Our model consists of four basic entities: 1) a user (with a mobile device), 2) a verifier (a shared car), 3) a group/revocation manager (a semi-trusted party who works as a system security provider with server and data storage), and 4) a service provider (vehicle owners' representative). In order to keep user privacy and unlinkability of user access to shared cars, we use a dynamic group signature scheme. After an initial

Figure 1: Proposed Privacy-Preserving Framework for Car-Sharing.

registration, the user is anonymous to observers and also to the service provider (that could be curious). Only the group/revocation manager can identify a user (after breaking the rules) by opening the key from the signature. Then the manager sends a fragment parameter from the user's group signature key to the service provider who can revoke all already issued tokens to this concrete user and prevent the user from acquiring new tokens. There can also be third parties/services involved that collect aggregate data and integrate shared-vehicle services such as smart city portals.

4.2 Used Cryptography

Our proposal employs updated cryptography methods such as the group signature scheme proposed by Kim *et al.* [12] (KSAP23). Technical details of this scheme are dense, therefore we use a brief formalism that helps us clarify the basic operations with the following notations:

- $\text{GroupSetup}(1^k)$: is an initial setup of a group public key gpk and group manager secret key $gmsk$ based on the chosen parameters and the security level (length) 1^k of the group signature scheme.
- $\text{Gsig}(gsk, gpk, m)$: is the group signature algorithm that takes as the input the group public key gpk , the secret key of the user (a signer) gsk and an input message m . The algorithm returns the signature o .
- $\text{GVerify}(o, m, gpk)$: is the group verification algorithm that takes as the input the group public key gpk , the signature o , and the input message m . The algorithm returns "true" if the signature is correct otherwise it returns "false".
- $\text{Revocation}(o, gmsk, \text{list of users' groupparams})$: the group manager can pair the valid signature and registered user parameters (groupparams) by using the group manager secret key $gmsk$. The output is a successfully traced user and the following revocation process (adding parameters to the blacklist).

Further, we use public key cryptography for digital signatures. We recommend using the post-quantum cryptography scheme:

Falcon [8] or the standard digital signature scheme based on elliptic curves such as the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA) [11]. The notation of operations is as follows:

- $\text{GeneratePKI}(1^k)$: is an initial setup of parameters and keys such as public key pk and private (secret) key sk .
- $\text{sig}(sk, m)$: is the digital signature algorithm that takes as the input the public key pk , the secret key of the user (a signer) sk , and an input message m . The algorithm returns signature o .
- $\text{Verify}(o, m, pk)$: is the verification algorithm that takes as the input the public key pk , the signature o , and the input message m . The algorithm returns "true" if the signature is correct otherwise it returns "false".

4.3 System Phases

The framework can be divided into these basic system phases as follows:

- (1) **Setup phase** - during this phase, all static entities (group/revocation manager, service provider) generate cryptography parameters and keys for schemes such as public key digital signatures and certificates for Transport Layer Security (TLS) secure connections (to the service provider, to the group/revocation manager, to the data storage, to the third parties).
- (2) **Registration/Join phase** - a new user joins the system and registers with the service provider and the group/revocation manager. The operations are depicted in Figure 2 and described as follows: Firstly, all public keys and certificates (from static entities) are distributed to users or the user downloads them from valid repositories within a user application (Step 1). Secondly, the user initiates the registration by sending the Join system request containing his/her ID, public key upk , and the digital signature of these data (o_1). The service provider verifies o_1 and stores o_1 , the user's ID, and the public key to the database (Step 2). Thirdly, the service provider responds with their signature o_2 which serves as the confirmation of the user registration at the service provider side (Step 3). Then (Step 4), the user starts a join phase with the group/revocation manager to establish his/her secret key gsk in the group signature scheme. The user sends the manager the Join group request message with two signatures o_2 (a confirmation of his/her registration) and o_3 (a commitment to his/her generated user group secret key) in Step 5. The manager verifies both signatures and finishes the join phase of the group signature scheme by adding the user to the group and to the data storage which stores the user's public key and user group parameters for potential revocation in the future. The process is finished by the confirmation in Step 6 and by Step 7 (establishing the group user secret key). The user is now in the group with his/her group secret key that corresponds to the group public key (gpk).
- (3) **Token Acquiring phase** - in this phase, the registered user can anonymously use the service and book the vehicle by a token request. In order to authorize his/her token request, the group digital signature scheme is used. The operations are depicted in Figure 3. The user prepares a token' that

contains requested parameters such as the chosen shared vehicle, sharing time duration, and other parameters with an ephemeral public key tpk for this token. This token' is signed by the user group secret key gsk and the group signature o_4 and token' are sent to the service provider securely by TLS. The service provider firstly checks the signature by gpk and then controls if this anonymous request was not produced by a revoked user. This is done by checking the part of signature parameters and the parameters (Rev) in the blacklist, more details in the origin group signature scheme [12]. If the anonymous user and signature o_4 are valid (not in the blacklist), the service provider creates a final *token* based on the requested parameters in *token'* and signs this by its private key for the chosen digital signature scheme. This signature o_5 is securely sent to the user who verifies it and will use it in the vehicle access and return phases.

- (4) **Vehicle Access phase** - this phase is between the user and a verifier device inside a shared vehicle. The operations of this phase are depicted in Figure 4. The user sends the access request initialization via a wireless proximity connection interface, e.g., Near Field Communication (NFC) or Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), to the verifier. The verifier generates a random nonce and sends it back to the user. Then, the user creates the signature o_6 by the ephemeral private key tsk for signing the token and commits this action to the nonce, the access phase by the "Access" string, and the provider signature o_5 . The verifier should check a token's validity (valid time, valid vehicle ID, etc.) and if the token is not revoked on the blacklist. If these control procedures are OK, it continues by verifying both signatures o_5 and o_6 . If both signatures are valid, the verifier sends the OK message back to the user's device and opens the vehicle for the user. If any of the procedures above is invalid, the access response message "NOT" is sent to the user, and the vehicle remains locked.
- (5) **Vehicle Returning phase** - this phase is between the user and the verifier device inside the shared vehicle and with the service provider. The operations of this phase are depicted in Figure 5. The user sends the return request initialization via a wireless proximity connection interface (NFC or BLE) to the verifier. The verifier generates a random nonce and sends it back to the user. Then, the user creates the signature o_6 by the ephemeral private key tsk for signing the token and commits this action to the nonce, the return phase by the "Return" string and the provider signature o_5 . The verifier should check the token's validity (if the user returns the vehicle within the approved time, correct valid vehicle ID, etc.). If the control procedures are OK, it continues by verifying both signatures o_5 and o_6 . If both signatures are valid, the verifier sends the confirmation message with *VID*, *time*, and *location* back to the user's device and locks the vehicle. These data are also sent with an applied token to the service provider to keep the actual location of the returned vehicle and store information about the provided service.
- (6) **Revocation phase** - in specific cases, when users break the rules, e.g., repeated expired returns, or caused vehicle damages, the system provider can start the revocation of the

Figure 2: Registration/Join phase.

Figure 3: Token Acquiring phase.

Figure 4: Vehicle Access phase.

Figure 5: Vehicle Returning phase.

user. The process is depicted in Figure 6. Firstly, the provider sends the revocation request with a concrete reason, token' and group signature o_4 to the group/revocation manager. The manager takes this group signature, the message that the token' is to enter the revocation procedure of the group signature scheme, and it can pair the user group parameters that lead to its public key upk in the database. These parameters are sent back to the service provider who adds the user group parameters Rev to the blacklist and also is able, based on upk , to reveal the user identity and to revoke all issued tokens to this specific user. These revoked tokens are added to the blacklist of tokens and are distributed to the concrete vehicles. If the revoked user was to try to acquire a new token (Step 5), his/her part of the signature would cause a match in the blacklist of the users' table with a specific Rev parameter. The concrete details about the group signature procedure are described in [12]. The access of the user will be denied by the response message (Step 6).

(7) **Third Party Interaction phase** - the vehicle sharing systems are often connected with other services and information portals. In this phase, we assume that the service provider can share some statistical data with other parties. The provider employ data aggregation or other suitable PETs. The provider should not share any concrete data containing user identities.

5 EVALUATION

In this section, we assess our proposal and present an informal system security analysis and performance evaluation.

5.1 Security Evaluation

In the proposed car-sharing solution, the authentication of the online servers, i.e., Group and Revocation Manager (GRM), Service provider (SP), and Data storage, is guaranteed by the TLS protocol

Figure 6: Revocation phase.

at least in version 1.2, Public Key Infrastructure (PKI), and Certification Authorities (CAs). Additionally, TLS provides also transmitted data integrity, authenticity, confidentiality, and resistance against replay attacks (i.e., freshness). On the other hand, the user authentication is based on our proprietary solution using group signatures and anonymized access tokens. While the freshness of the authentication sessions is provided by the TLS protocol in case of communication to the online services, the freshness within the authentication to the Shared Vehicle (SV) is guaranteed via a lightweight challenge/response authentication protocol. Below, we provide the security analysis of features that are closely related to the user authentication processes. Note that our car-sharing system deploys a user authentication protocol on three different communication levels: 1) communication with the GRM, 2) communication with the SP, and 3) communication with the SV.

- **Soundness and completeness** - guarantee that valid authentication proofs generated by authorized users will be always verified correctly (i.e., the guaranty of completeness property), and invalid proofs will always fail verification (i.e., the guaranty of soundness property). These security properties must hold on all three communication levels:

- 1 User authentication to the GRM is based on using tokens consisting of the SP signature $o_2 = sig(spsk; OK, upk)$ on user public key upk and upk itself. During the Registration/Join phase, a user proves the knowledge of the corresponding secret key usk by computing the signature $o_3 = sig(usk; tau)$. As the usk is known only to a specific registered user and it is tightly bound to the public key upk which is digitally signed by SP, the protocol fulfills both properties of soundness and completeness.
- 2 User authentication to the SP is based on using a group signature scheme. During the Token Acquiring phase, a user generates a group signature $o_4 = Gsig(gsk; token')$ on its access token $token'$ using its user group secret key gsk . As the gsk is known only to the specific group member and it is tightly bound to the group public key gpk which

is a part of the system parameters, the protocol fulfills both properties of soundness and completeness.

- 3 User authentication to the SV is based on using access tokens issued by SP. The token includes a token public key tpk . During the Vehicle Access/Returning phase, a user proves a knowledge of the corresponding token secret key tsk . As the tsk is known only to the user owning the token and it is tightly bound to the token public key tpk which is a part of the access token signed by SP, the protocol fulfills both properties of soundness and completeness.
- **User anonymity** - protects system users from being profiled and tracked by the SP. In fact, all communication to the SP within the Token Acquiring, Vehicle Access, and Vehicle Returning phases are anonymous and do not reveal any personal information allowing them to be linked to the individual real identity. All this is ensured by using group signatures in case of communication with the SP and using anonymized access tokens when communicating with the SV. The SP receives only the information that a valid group member requests an access token, without knowing his/her real identity. The SV receives only the information that the owner of the valid access token requests access to the vehicle, without knowing more information about the token owner. Note that the GRM does not know the real identity of the system user either. The only information that it gets during the Registration/Join phase is the user public key upk of the registered user.
 - **User unlinkability** - prevents profiling of users in terms of the possibility of finding out if two different valid authentication proofs were generated by the same user or not. This security property is applied in the Token Acquiring phase to protect users (even anonymous users) from being profiled and tracked by the SP. In other words, the SP is not able to distinguish from the reservations whether the SV is being reserved by the same user or by different users. This property is guaranteed by using group signatures.

- **Token unforgeability** - ensures that only the SP can create a valid access token. This security property is ensured by using asymmetric cryptography. Each access token is signed by SP using its *spsk*. Without knowledge of *spsk*, nobody can forge the access token.
- **Token non-delegability** - prevents the passing of tokens between users. This security property is ensured by using asymmetric cryptography. Each access token includes its token public key *tpk* of which the secret key *tsk* is securely stored in a user authentication device (e.g., a smartphone) and never leaves it. Without the knowledge of the *tsk*, nobody can use the access token.
- **Non-repudiation** - of actions for user access and return phases. This security property is ensured by using asymmetric cryptography. Each access token includes its token public key *tpk* of which the secret key *tsk* is securely stored in a user authentication device (e.g., a smartphone) and never leaves it. Without knowledge of *tsk*, nobody can use the access token. Therefore, if a user performs a valid access/return phase using the access token, then it means that the user knows the corresponding *tsk*, and therefore, he/she cannot deny in the future that he/she took this action. Note that the unique ownership of an access token by a specific user is also undeniable. In fact, *tpk* is part of the access token *token'* and on which the anonymous user created the signature $o_4 = Gsig(gsk; token')$. This signature is anonymous and is stored locally by the SP. However, by opening this signature $o_4 = Gsig(gsk; token')$, the GRM can link the signature to a specific user public key *upk*, which can be then linked to the real identity of the user by the SP. All the above steps are undeniable as every user action was performed by using digital signatures which guarantee the non-repudiation property.
- **Traceability** - enables the SP to trace back the real identity of malicious users of the system. However, for this purpose, the cooperation of the GRM and the SP is needed. Based on the SP request consisting of user access token *token'* and corresponding group signature $o_4 = Gsig(gsk; token')$ of the malicious user to the GRM, the GRM will return the public key *upk* of the corresponding user. The SP can then link this public key to the user's real identity. The SP can also prove that the *upk* belongs to a specific user as the specific user used the corresponding secret key *usk* to generate the signature $o_1 = sig(usk; ID, upk)$ on this public key *upk* during the Registration/Join phase.
- **Revocation** - enables the SP to revoke malicious users from the system. However, to do so, the cooperation of the GRM and the SP is needed. Based on the SP request consisting of user access token *token'* and corresponding group signature $o_4 = Gsig(gsk; token')$ of the malicious user to the GRM, the GRM will return the corresponding revocation parameters Rev_{x+1} . The SP can then use these revocation parameters to identify revoked anonymous users within the Registration/Join phase, and therefore, reject the request to issue a new access token to them.

5.2 Performance Evaluation of Main Phases

Our solution consists of digital and group signature operations. Table 1 shows which cryptographic operations are required in the main phases and provides an indicative comparison with the most relevant work that was proposed by Groza *et al.* [9] and also used group signatures, the PRESTvO solution.

It is to be noted that IdSig and IdVer represent the signature and verification phases of identity-based signature schemes used in PRESTvO. These phases are usually more expensive than common digital signatures such as RSA. PRESTvO suggests two types of identity-based signature schemes: GQ90 [10] and Shamir's S85 [19]. The S85 scheme provides better performance (5 to 10 times) than the GQ90 scheme on various devices, for concrete results please see [9]. PRESTvO also offers the on-the-fly variant of the execute phase that is based only on symmetric cryptography (3x Message Authentication Codes). In both schemes, we do not compare less expensive symmetric cryptography operations. Nonetheless, we can consider the signing and verification phases of group signatures as the most expensive operations. We assume that schemes use 128-bit curves, e.g., KSAP employs BLS12-381 curve with $|G_1| = 382$ b, $|G_2| = 763$ b, and $|Z_p| = 256$ b.

PRESTvO deploys the group signature BBS04 that requires for signing: 9 exponentiations in G_1 , 3 exponentiations in G_T , and for verification: 1 pairing, 8 exponentiations in G_1 , 2 exponentiations in G_2 , and 3 exponentiations in G_T . The signature length is 2682 b (composed from 3 $|G_1|$ and 6 $|Z_p|$).

Our solution deploys the group signature KSAP23 that requires for signing: 12 exponentiations in G_1 and for verification: 3 pairings and 10 exponentiations in G_1 . The signature length is 5352 b (composed of 6 $|G_1|$ and 3 $|Z_p|$). We decide to use the KSAP23 scheme that allows efficient revocation in our solution despite it being less efficient than BBS04. Overall, our solution is more compact compared to PRESTvO which has more atomic operations in main phases as acquiring tokens and accessing cars. Our future steps aim at the proof-of-concept implementation, testing in real devices, and providing concrete runtimes for the phases.

6 CONCLUDING REMARKS

In this work, we presented main legislative, security and privacy issues and threats in car-sharing services. Further, we proposed the efficient and practical privacy-preserving security solution for car-sharing systems based on modern cryptography schemes. We use dynamic group signatures for protecting the privacy of honest users. Comparing to the related works, our designed solution allows the instant revocation of users that break rules in the system, and is more practical for constrained devices in vehicles as omit expensive operations in access and return phases. The presented evaluation results indicate how used countermeasures and methods will affect the system performance with a simply comparison of basic phases with the related work. Our solution deploys less operations and is more compact for a practical deployment in small and middle open car-sharing solutions. Our security analysis demonstrate how privacy and security properties are addresses in the provided design.

In future work, we will focus on the beta implementation and field tests on real vehicles. Another future work will include the investigation of the post-quantum variants with digital signature and

Table 1: Performance Comparison of Phases in Privacy-preserving Car-Sharing Systems.

Phase:	This work	PRESTvO (Groza <i>et al.</i> [9])
Registration / Setting	3 Sig/Ver	7 IdSig/IdVer
Acquiring / Delegation	1 Sig/Ver + 1 Gsig/Gver	2 Gsig/Gver + 2 IdSig/IdVer
Access / Execute	1 Sig/Ver	(1 Gsig/Gver or 1 IdSig/IdVer) + 1 IdSig/IdVer
Return	1 Sig/Ver	not proposed
Revocation	1 GS Revocation	not described

group signature schemes and the evaluation of their performance on various platforms used by users and vehicles. Finally, we plan to expand the analysis and evaluation of legal regulations for car sharing systems in EU.

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